

Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG emission estimates

Graciosa meteorological conditions – February 2026

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The overall weather situation in February 2026 is presented in Figs. 1 & 2 by the average daily courses and variability of 30-minute values of basic meteorological elements, turbulent heat and CO₂ fluxes, and basic turbulence indices. The variability of meteorological elements can be defined as typical for an oceanic climate. The average daily amplitude of air temperature T was only 2.3°C, and relative humidity did not exceed 10%. The minimum observed air temperature was 8.4°C, and the maximum, in several cases, exceeded 18°C. The absolute water vapor content in the air, p_{H2O}, varied from 7.7 to 22.1 ppt. During most days in February 2026, high values of incoming solar radiation K↓ were observed, with the maximum values exceeding 600 W·m⁻². The surface radiation balance also reached high values, exceeding 300 W·m⁻². Albedo throughout the month, during midday hours, was at ~0.23. Average wind speed values were 6.2 m·s⁻¹, with 30-minute data showing wind speeds exceeding 10 m·s⁻¹.

In February 2026, winds from the SW and W sectors dominated at the Graciosa ENA station (fig. 3). The month had good conditions for the development of turbulence in the vicinity of the measuring station (figs. 1 and 2). This is indicated by the values of turbulent sensible heat fluxes Q_H and latent heat fluxes Q_E, whose maximum 30-minute values exceeded 150 W·m⁻². The intensive development of turbulence is evidenced by both the distinct diurnal course of Q_H and Q_E with a maximum during the day, as well as the Obukhov length L or the stability parameter (negative values during the day, positive values at night). The heat flux into the ground Q_G played a marginal role in the energy balance. Another indicator of turbulence intensity, the friction velocity u*, also reached high values (an average of 0.70 m·s⁻¹ during the day and 0.67 m·s⁻¹ at night).

Figures 4 and 5 show that regardless of stability, the source area of the heat and CO₂ fluxes covered the land area. In the case of unstable conditions, this area had a diameter of about 200-300 meters. In the case of stable conditions, it was larger and had a diameter of about 300-400 meters. Negative values of CO₂ flux during the day (fig. 2) indicate intensive uptake of CO₂ by plants and release of this gas into the atmosphere at night (positive FCO₂). In addition, in February 2026, the latent heat flux was mainly positive, indicating that evaporation dominated the station environment regardless of the time of day. On the other hand, the sensible heat flux at night was characterized by negative values, which indicates that the ground in the station's surroundings cooled more intensively in relation to the overlying air.

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Fig. 1. Mean diurnal courses (left column) and 30-minute meteorological data in February 2026 on Graciosa ENA site operated by ARM (T – air temperature, RH – relative humidity, pH₂O – water vapor density, v – wind speed, u* - friction velocity, L – Obukhov length, (z-d)/L – stability parameter).

Fig. 2. Mean diurnal courses (left column) and 30-minute meteorological data in February 2026 on Graciosa ENA site operated by ARM (p – precipitation, p_{cum} – cumulative precipitation, Q^* - radiation balance, Q_H – sensible heat flux, Q_E -latent heat flux, Q_G - soil heat flux, $K\downarrow$ – shortwave solar downward radiation, $K\uparrow$ – shortwave solar reflected radiation, $L\downarrow$ – longwave downward radiation, $L\uparrow$ - longwave upward radiation, FCO_2 – carbon dioxide flux).

Fig. 3. Wind speed (v) and friction velocity (u^*) in relation to wind direction in February 2026 on the Graciosa ENA site operated by ARM.

Tab. 1. Minimum, mean, and maximum values of the air temperature T , relative humidity RH , wind speed v , friction velocity u^* , water vapor concentration ρ_{H_2O} , incoming solar radiation $K\downarrow$ and monthly total precipitation in February 2026 on Graciosa ENA site operated by ARM.

	T	RH	V	u^*	ρ_{H_2O}	$K\downarrow$	mean monthly albedo (when $K\downarrow > 30.0 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$)	monthly precipitation
	[°C]	[%]	[$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	[$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	[ppt]	[$\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$]	-	[mm]
Max	19.6	100.0	13.7	2.46	22.1	756.9	0.228	135.1
Mean	15.2	80.4	6.2	0.68	14.1	109.6		
Min	8.4	55.6	0.1	0.03	7.7	0.0		

Fig. 4. Source area of turbulent fluxes calculated for unstable conditions in February 2026. White solid lines indicate source area with $p=25, 50, 75$ and 90% , yellow dashed lines indicate $100, 200, 300$ and 400 m distance from the measurement site. Photo by Google.

Fig. 5. Source area of turbulent fluxes calculated for stable conditions in February 2026. White solid lines indicate source area with $p=25, 50, 75$ and 90% , yellow dashed lines indicate $100, 200, 300$ and 400 m distance from the measurement site. Photo by Google.